

**International Journal of Marketing & Financial
Management, Vol. 2, Issue 2, Mar-Apr-2014**

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349-2546 (Print)

IJMFM

MARKETING MECHANISM FOR SELLING PRODUCTS AND SERVICES IN INDIAN RURAL MARKETS

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Abstract

Agricultural commodities are gaining a higher acceptance in terms of higher prices and thus enabling the rural population to earn a higher income, this rises great scope for advanced and breathless efforts to be displayed by the marketers. In India especially rural marketing is gaining more and more importance day by day as reforms in agricultural sectors have highlighted the availability of huge untapped potential, which attracts marketers from India as well as MNCs in India selling their products and services in urban areas. This has also been supported by the infrastructure to go rural and market. Any strategy among the business level strategies would focus on accessibility, affordability and availability. There is a need to be more attentive so that the uncertainty reduction in management of this market place can be achieved with the market research. Moreover it has been observed that the price elasticity in such markets is highly dominating

other elastics. Hence there is no second thought that the division is visible between rural Indian market and urban Indian market. This article tries to examine differential suitable strategies and their scope for rural marketing and to highlight the issues and challenges with the current and commonly used generic strategies in rural marketing.

Key Word: *Rural market; rural potential; marketing strategies.*

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Reference this paper as: *Yusuf Kamal & Jaiswal .B (2014). “Marketing Mechanism For Selling Products And Services In Indian Rural Markets,” International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management, Vol. 2, Issue 2, Mar-Apr-2014, pp 01-14,*

Introduction:

The term rural marketing differs from person to person and that is where it leads to a poor diagnose practice for rural marketing and hence gives a misunderstanding in context with the prescriptions to treat such illness. As far as marketing structure is concern the rural marketing and urban marketing are pretty identical. However the rural marketing and rural markets have their own characteristics and difficulties to drop and select among the available opportunities. The rural market is more demanding and asks marketers to put in more efforts because of the noticeable increase in the income, at the same time they also need such products and service which will further increase the agricultural produce so that income once again can be increased. There are ample of opportunities for marketers due to vastness and demand base in rural market. Approximately two third of the country resides in rural areas and approximately 50 percent of the income comes from agricultural produce hence it is clear that in India rural markets are the major stakes in the overall Indian Market. India consists approximately 455 districts and approximately 640000 villages, which any marketer may further highlight in reference with demographical parameters,

thus this special stake dominates the remaining Indian market's stakes, which is looking forward for expansion of marketing practices in this category not only because it dominates but also they aspire a better life and welfare in rural areas.

With the help of the rural micro finance, agricultural reforms and advancement in the agricultural technologies, rural market is offering tremendous untapped chunk which can be converted into profit. Development plans like MNREGA and other social securities offered through the governance within the boundaries of health, education, agriculture, allied activities, communication, and rural electrification has changed the lifestyle of rural population which is still under acceptable literacy rate from lower income group and have seasonal employment opportunities, based on these symptoms this would not be incorrect to forecast that in future the rural markets will dominate the sales figures of urban market. Since the urban market is no more offering rise in sales figures beyond a certain limit and those who still have some room to increase the sale figure may not have the same characteristics in future, hence the executives are getting attracted and never mind to include the rural sales in their existing marketing profile to enlarge the

market share. This idea has almost occupied most of the corporate, companies like Godrej Group which is present from personal care products and services to agri foods do not hesitate in such engagements. And it just looks like that the rural consumers are careless about the quality and branding which is a myth. National Council for Applied Economic Research indicates that the rural income is maintaining the pace with the urban income. As compared with the urban income in 1994-95 from 55% to 58% the rural income has shifted up by 63% to 64% in 2001-02 and has touched approximately 66% by 2004-05. The 12% growth is visible in rural middle class which compliments urban income growth i.e. 13% and the upper income class especially those with the household income above than the Rupees one million per year is expected to further rise up to Rupees twenty one million by the year 2009-10 from four million in 2001-02. And this consists of 23% to 24% rural share. Hence higher rural income means bigger markets.

Rural Indian market pays approximately 1.7 billion US Dollars for automobiles purchases and more than one billion US Dollars for durables. In total this market representing value of about 27 billion US Dollars.

Even MNCs are focussing on rural India and have planned a long term pool generation which will yield long lasting revenue. Few years ago Coke created venture with hinterland and now its rural growth is approximately 37% where its urban growth is in contrast reflects 24%. Coke is pioneer in tempting rural lure, its global competitor Pepsico took a wider aspect to trade and commerce and has allowed to set shop in late 80s and invested in food processing & farming which was pre-condition for the entry.

To push Unilever products in to its surroundings all over the country, Project-Shakti along with self help groups was used as a basic tool, its four dimensional proposal throws income generation for rural women, best practices in health and hygiene was spreader which enables improvement in rural quality of life, strengthen the rural community by crafting access to adequate information with the help of community portals and this also supports NGOs in spreading literacy. In 12 states covering approximately 61400 villages at present there are about 15500 entrepreneurs with the project Shakti and women are in majority as far as numbers of entrepreneur are concern.

All such facts and figures are attracting bigger business houses to rush and enter into rural business in order to expand. Mahindra and Mahindra is a well known name in farm equipment, its unit Mahindra Shubh Labh is operating in 11 states and leverages a concrete Mahindra brand name, there is 410 plus dealer network with 700000 Mahindra tractor customers, with a vision to offer entire range of products/services to enhance farming results and it also bridges/simplifies the commodity market supply chain. Its retail unit Mahindra Krishi Vihar has been sensitive enough in a significant increment in the groundnut farming in Rajasthan this was made possible because of a new seed which was bought from Maharashtra, also in Maharashtra variety of grapes was introduced under the same umbrella. Estimated rural India is worth 27 billion US Dollar. There is no second thought that even MNCs are going bold enough to accept the fact that the rural India would be source of their survival. Broadly rural marketing includes the marketing of rural industries products, agricultural products and many services which are closely related with the rural occupation pattern. State agencies, cooperatives, processors are some of the recurring trade channels which are present in rural areas. Anyhow a village economy or a

social cluster itself cannot be developed in absence of rural marketing, negligible planning for rural marketing is present, where as the marketing in itself is a dynamic state of indulge and is just a portion of whole economy. Hence two facets of coin which is village economy are production and marketing. Rural marketing is the nervous system of rural development activities.

Rural marketing is anyways a two way marketing system where flow of products and services is not only towards rural areas but it also encompasses the movement of products from rural areas to urban areas; hence rural marketing can be defined as a practice of identification of need of rural consumer in respect with the routine as well as professional life, which tries to catch the satisfaction in form of utility related with the agriculture produce of indirect influence over the agricultural produce, by supplying the goods as services in accordance”.

Because of the two ways process visible in rural marketing, this paper tries to point the issues and challenges associated with the strategies for rural marketing, it also covers rural produce and strategies thereof followed to end the process with satisfaction with special reference if Indian Rural Market.

STRATEGIES FOR RURAL MARKETING

About two decades ago the biggest problem for the corporate was to prioritize the target location this was due to the unstructured rural market however rural market has changed in last few years, earlier agro based companies were able to concentrate in this market with a negligible promotional campaigns and innovative strategies, weak distribution system was present at the same time lack of technology and literacy were the prominent forces for poor availability of products and awareness among the villagers about the availability of such solution which will satisfy their need. Gradually by the companies it was realized that there was dispersion, stiff competition and disorder in the urban market, and it was experienced that the demand in rural areas has been built up. With the figure that the approximately 72% of population in Indian lives in rural areas, companies started focusing on this high potential and unexplored cluster. Companies started offering products like two rupees Parle g tikki pack biscuits, one rupee sachet chic shampoo, customized televisions by LG, Marico's shanti Amla hair oil and all such offers shown a positive response in the sales figures. "Project Bharat" campaign by Hindustan Lever in 1999 offered the trails across the country

and estimation said that the 30% of the total personal care products are growing at the rate of 50% with the five years time frame, and the target in first phase was to increase awareness by 41% over a set of population of approximately 11.55 million rural households.

Second phase began with the "Project Jagruti" by Colgate Palmolive in the year 2001 which was solely dedicated to the village consumers contact programme, and this uplifted the penetration of dental cream offered by the Colgate Palmolive from 33000 to 55000, with a reach of one million household. Such plans are feasible enough for the penetration increment in rural areas.

This resulted in a practical and visible association of various categories and brands which were occupying their places in rural stores and such retail out were also multiplied by the significant number in the rural areas. The high assembly areas like fairs/Mela etc. are taken as the effective marketing tool as a huge population can be captured as a target audience. In marketing location plays an important character. Hence if a product is been targeted for kids the places like anganwadi and schools are the best places in order to bind the kids and mothers who will act as the influencers.

Similarly for branded products village influencers and mandis are the best option to push the products.

SOME POPULAR AND CURRENTLY USED STRATEGIES IN RURAL MARKETING

Quality perception with the best possible Promotion

Use of new technology which helps companies to communicate in context with the products and services offered. There exist a trade off between communication by company and quality perceived by the customers. Therefore such positioning of technology becomes very important. The Indian customers' perception about the expected product is changing, now the customers can understand the difference between utilities derived from a product/services and product/services. Indian rural customers always want the balance between money paid and utility derived and the current market scenario especially with the companies offering services the value for money has a different equation and the variables like recurring value derived from the product and services defines that how this equation would be balanced.

With the case of Celebrity Endorsement, use of right person such as Indian Models and actors for promotion of products and services certifies that the manufacturer is of Indian origin. Omega, a multinational and a premium brand in quartz clock manufacturing have chosen Diana Hayden and Shahrukh Khan for the advertisements despite of the fact that they have Cindy Crawford as another ready option, and this helps Omega to display that there are of Indian origin, another case where Pantene Shampoo manufacturers have chosen Penelope Cruz for the advertising which could have been taken as more effective by the use of Indian Celebrity.

Rural Market and effective Communication

Companies for communication in Rural Market have selected the local language for promotion of the products and services; this is visible by the different wall painting (as advertisement) and other outdoor Medias, by telecommunication companies in rural areas where concept of quality has been promoted with the effective and understandable manner of communication and this is more effective with the use of local language.

Strategies as per the rural consumer Dynamics

Today the rural customer need more and more branded products and excellent services. Value for money has been the prime area of concern with the rural market customer and they were never price sensitive, they can pay for premium products and services offered by the expensive brands provided that the brand offers them additional utility. In context with the Social and Cultural values with the rural customers, companies have realized that they hold very strong stimuli on the customers in rural markets, hence regards should be displayed in reference with their cultural and social values in order to promote the products and services in rural markets.

Practice to track the need of customer and offering the same

Companies calculate the additional amount of the value which has been expected by the customers due to the tendency in customers of computation of value for money regardless of the additional value associated along with the products, they aim for essential functionality. However in case seller is offering frills without any additional charges then customers feel delighted. Apart

from the knowledge acquired by the sellers that what is needed by the customers, it is also necessary to track that which is the stimuli which will create positive feeling within the customer and this will also help them to act as influencers. This is end of core marketing practice where companies will have to only and only indulge themselves in finding out the real satisfaction area by consuming the product and services.

Products/Services and devotion towards nation

Nokia introduced the ring tone "sare jahan se accha" with the model 5110, this shows their concern about the nation and this ways they have also associated themselves with patriotism, then this also invites rural consumers that the purchase of such products by them must be priority and a devotion towards their nation. Also some companies do advertising on occasion Republic Day and Independence Day associating the forum of such celebrations which is again sensitive enough to create the feeling of association with the nation. Hence such promotional stunts are result oriented and ensure the presence of products in rural markets.

Sports spirit Impact: Cricket team and product promotion

Hero Honda launched a campaign during the cricket world cup with a slogan “Dhak Dhak Go”, this way they have associated themselves as the supporter of Indian Cricket team and this sensation actually started supporting product and manufacturers even after the event is over. Companies are also indulging in co sponsoring and sponsoring Indian cricket teams so that the association of company with the mega and popular event can be cashed. Some other events like film fare award distribution ceremonies are also not free enough with such stunts, and initiate the purchase habits among the rural customers. This is a general tendency of human that he/she tries to associate himself/herself with such products and services with which they and others visualize themselves with the event and by this they also become loyal towards company and products.

Niche Marketing and Segment based positioning

Samsung's cellular phone model GT-E1200T offer approximately 10 days standby battery backup and has been especially designed for rural customers and offers an uninterrupted connectivity to rural

customers even when there are long power cuts. Electrolux is trying to develop a refrigerator which can offer a long lasting cooling even with the long power cuts. Hence this is another area where companies are trying to find out the specific needs of the customers, with the special circumstances lying with customers, and the companies position themselves with the help of segments and positioning their products in front of rural market with such strategies.

Communication and efficiency of Medias

Traditional media used by the marketers is puppetry, folk theatres and melas for the promotion and communication; whereas the modern media includes Television, e chaupals, radio, and promotional SMS through the cell phones and recorded call to the cell numbers who are not registered as Do Not Disturb (DND) numbers. LIC and Government of India uses puppet in order to educate rural masses, while ITC's e chaupal has been an exceptional initiative in Indian history, where approximately 1.5 million of the rural population gets in range of the communicator and it has presence over five states with approximately 2500 chaupals. The use of such electronic chaupal kind of platforms and mass communication with the SMS alerts and recorded calls are gaining

much popularity in the field of rural communication hence there lies an ample opportunity to use such medias and craft the communication strategy with the use of such media presence of products can be ensured in rural markets.

Distribution channels and strategy which offers more space for localized channels

Big supermarkets and glamorous selling floors where customers have ample of merchandise in display and lot many more with air conditioning and fabulous physical evidences will not attract the rural consumers to initiate the purchase and they have the apprehension that such environment is made of their own money and hence will be recovered with high pricing system of the companies selling products and services. The channel which starts right from their life style and traditional routine, is convenient enough and more effective in rural marketing, some of the distribution channels which are commonly used by the companies are Local Panwal, Baniya and Kirana wala, they not only connect the rural customer with companies along with the feeling of affiliation but also appears as some low priced products.

DIFFICULTIES IN RURAL MARKETING

Indian rural market is mode enough in terms of high degree of ethnic, regional and cultural diversity, their basic source of income for their survival is agriculture. The total GDP of India consist of approximately 25% agricultural produce, It also contributes about 14% of India's total export, also approximately 59% of the India's total population gets employment from agriculture which is approximately for 651 million people. Despite of all such relevant facts and contributions, the relative improvement in terms of the rural people's life and their around development is not that satisfactory, they are still surviving with huge power cuts with minimum infrastructural facilities for business as well as for their social obligations.

Rural market has started showing the high demand and is now looks like segment of market which has potential much higher than the urban markets. Rural marketing is all about four **Rs**

- ✓ **Reaching** customers,
- ✓ **Reading** their wants,
- ✓ **Realization** of distribution channels and ultimately
- ✓ **Releasing** customer satisfaction

It is a myth that the agricultural inputs like fertilizer, seeds, pesticides and agricultural machinery just have the high potential in rural market, However there is a potential beyond the imagination for consumer goods in rural market which is showing growth rate of about five times as compared with the urban counterpart.

Rural Marketing and Challenges

For any company targeting rural market it is not possible to enter into rural market and occupy larger rural market share, when rural markets in advance offering high degree of fascination:

Literacy Rate

Literacy rate is less than 35% in rural areas, where the urban market shows literacy rate of about 52%, this looks like a big threat for companies offering products and services in rural areas where it is really hard to convince customer despite of the fact that every other marketing tool is been well aligned as per the marketing plan.

Seasonal Demand

Due to monsoon and other climatic situation the entire income of rural population is fluctuating there by with external and

uncontrollable factors, hence the purchasing power is something secondary however the events which are favourable and unfavourable are primary forces which will sketch of the rural demand, so the irregularity and instability is the prominent feature and challenge in the rural markets.

Supply Chain

There are so many tiers in rural distribution channel which are deliberate in increasing the complexities and unmanageability, the effective distribution scheme requires village shopkeepers, mandal whole sellers/dealers, district level stockist and companies' own depot for the state distribution and supply, where as the urban market distribution channel is simple despite that it has tier system which works at the same horizon of location.

Rural life style and role of Traditions

New practices and their adoption is not an easy task for rural customers, this can be understood with the imaginary situation when even a rich farmer, who is even educated would avoid wearing jeans and sports shoes.

Buying decisions

Less speed and delayed rural decisions are more visible in rural customers than the urban customers; also they feel more comfortable when they have a trail attempt for the utility of that product and services which need to be purchased. This attempt is necessary to ensure that there is a self endorsed guarantee that the purchase will give the satisfaction about value for money and utility.

Promotion and Media

Television over the Radio holds a unique beneficiary and they both simultaneously show their unmatched features of communication in rural market, however the reach of the both mentioned Medias is relatively lesser over the rural households, and therefore the option left with the companies is only participation in exhibitions and fairs for the promotional activities. This option has effectiveness but is occasional and if somehow the frequency of its occurrence will be increased then its efficiency will be lost. This is another challenging part for the companies targeting the rural market.

Career planning in rural market

Specialized talent is needed in order to build up the career in rural market, it is not that

simple and easy to pursue career with rural market in rural market, there are certain customised abilities which grooms the personality of a sales person as well as a manager which look after the one rural territory. And lack of such specialized management trainees and their willingness to opt for the rural marketing becomes more challenging for the companies to manage rural markets.

Culture

Shared values, perceptions, and beliefs are even different in one common rural market when there is diversification of rural population with in religion, occupation, caste, age, education, income and politics, and these forces try to insert their own place when decision making comes in context with the product purchase it becomes difficult to control the behaviour of people in rural market. Rural people believe that the formal education is not that important to live life comfortably as the experience is needed, hence they have their own style of mixing the product utility with the practicality of the purchase, they oblige the sales persons who are successful enough in reflecting the practical solutions against the problems, still a tailored training is needed in order to overcome impression that product

practicality is not just the way to judge the purchase wisdom but it is also essential that the theoretical aspects about the purchase are inseparable. These trainings will allow sales persons to align themselves in settling down with the rural market operations.

The complete solution is not just the training part but since the rural people are the masses which are heterogeneous, hence the reach till such consumers is also a successive challenge, and then they role of assumptions that such products have a high profit margins hence they should be avoided.

Future Trends

Companies who are not able to generate substantial profit in the urban market can balance their imbalances by exploiting the rural markets, this ways not only the lost volume of profit will be restored but also a new trend can be set with other lines of business with one corporate holding many lines of businesses. If the rural market comes in limelight then the brightness of the industry who is pioneer will also increase.

CONCLUSION

Rural Marketing is a developing thought and is the potential in an economy which is untapped; Marketers' community know that

this going to be the crafting tool of the profitability of almost every business in future. For those who are willing to cater the rural market must look for improved infrastructure and fulfilment of promise is the light of their future. There is very clear that all the macro-level strategies must focus on 3 As (Availability, Accessibility and Affordability). Even scanning and filtration of ideas & plans is a mandate. Spotlight attention is needed in market research for those who want to reduce the uncertainty during the management of these markets. Moreover in rural areas the demand looks like a highly price elastic issue, break in price barrier in rural areas is necessary, and this will ensure the separation of grey area with local brands. There is no second thought that division between urban and rural India exist, however it looks like that the seamless integration of urban and rural markets is on its way along with the path of silent revolution and there are many new and innovative ideas in terms of planning for rural need to be invented. The comprehensive frame for rural marketing in the form of marketing mix for rural market must be therefore taken into consideration in order to start up the segments with the right product/service, considering value for expenditure in pricing, selection of the

appropriate most channels for distribution, preferring the long term relationships with the stakeholders and customers and use of potential of emotional brands. The rural market/segment is not uniform the independent choice in this market is not very big, although the general size is very large. There are demographical, geographical, logistical and statistical differences in rural India. When it comes to formulate the rural market strategy, the realities and positioning in context with the market segments lie and appear different for different clusters.

Today rural consumers are not going to nearby cities to buy the branded product and services; this brings in the opportunity for all the global players to ensure their presence in rural market where customers are more throwing opportunities area for especially Fast Moving Consumer Goods or retailing (either banking or insurance). Only 8% to 10% of the rural population has the life insurance coverage this explains that the upcoming scenario will display the maximum opportunities in this stream of rural market. Lot many companies are trying to tap the rural customers and are on the way to develop cost effective channels of distribution. Syndicate distribution, direct selling with the help of delivery vans,

construction of temporary stalls in exhibitions/melas are some popular and accelerating examples. Companies like Unilever, Godrej and ITC have found the role of stockist and its sales force successful enough in direct sales to rural customers. Rural markets are shaping them as emerging direct market centres. Additional and innovative sales channel which has been tried by Hindustan Unilever is the project shakti's association with the Self Help Groups (SHGs) in their current business opportunities, this is done with help of motive that the SHGs will have a belongingness sense with HUL as their small scale distributors, this model is suitable most for the FMGC companies and reduces cost to a greater extent and this is also helpful in penetration of rural markets.

Companies must keep this mind that the customer is not magpie, they are just refining their search with a perspective that they would find cheapest product, as they set value for money as priority in every attempt of their purchase. Hence pricing looks like a prime factor which advocates cost opportunity and cost-benefit advantage. Price should be value offer which is affordable, this is supported because price sensitivity is very high and habit to compare

price is another feature of rural customers. Budget is not the major constraint for the rural customer but the cash inflow is quite time consuming and lengthier this challenge may be eradicated with the help of small packs/sizes of the products and services which are relatively offering a lesser quantity and hence they can be purchased with minimum burden on the budget, also this area explains that if there is cash inflow crunch the marketer can offer the financial products, solutions or schemes which are suitable for them.

As a concluding remark hence, if a company is willing to occupy the rural market, they should have first the comprehensive and intense analysis of the rural market goal, targeting the predefined characteristics of rural population and employ different marketing strategies in accordance with real situations.

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